

NEW DEVELOPMENTS WITH SHORT STAPLE ALUMINA FIBRES IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

J Dinwoodie and I Horsfall
ICI Chemicals and Polymers Group,
Research and Technology Department,
The Heath, Runcorn, Cheshire. WA7 4QD

ABSTRACT

The flexibility of the alumina fibre production process allows controlled variations of the porous and crystalline microstructure. As a result, key fibre properties such as strength, modulus, hardness and density may be tailored to meet the performance and weight saving requirements of the MMC application. The properties of an extruded aluminium matrix composite made by a powder metallurgy route indicate the potential for using short aligned fibres in engine parts traditionally made from steel. However, to exploit fully the reinforcing potential of both low density (2.1g/cm^3) and high density (3.3g/cm^3) fibres in squeeze cast aluminium and magnesium matrix composites will require improved control over interfacial reactions involving fibre, matrix and the binder used in the manufacture of the preforms.

INTRODUCTION

The driving force behind new automotive engine design work is the need to build lightweight units capable of delivering higher performance, improved fuel economy and lower emission and noise levels. The potential for saving weight by substitution of fibre reinforced aluminium for cast iron is considerable: as a rough guide, there is around 98kg cast iron in a small economy car, approximately 12% of the vehicle weight, with most of this located in the engine. The cast iron content increases to 15-17% in a typical diesel truck.

Fibre reinforcement also enables aluminium to continue to meet ever-increasing performance requirements in for example pistons and cylinder heads. In pistons for advanced diesel engines, where the crown, ring groove and pin boss areas are subjected to higher thermal and mechanical loads as peak cylinder pressures are increased, we find excellent examples of the benefits of fibre reinforcement. Amongst the property advantages to be gained are higher modulus, improved tensile and

fatigue strength (particularly at elevated temperatures), a lower coefficient of thermal expansion and superior wear properties (1). The technology which has been established to develop these composite pistons is now being extended to other engine parts such as connecting rods, piston pins, cylinder liners and areas of the cylinder head and valve train (2). Table 1 gives the key material properties. The potential saving in reciprocating mass by replacement of cast iron and steel in these parts will result in a 'cascade' effect on other parts such as the crankshaft and bearings; further benefits in reduced vibration and noise attenuation can also be expected.

The effect of material substitution on fuel economy is generally difficult to assess since this will also depend on engine size, aerodynamic styling and mode of driving etc., but in the commercial vehicle business the benefits in terms of increased payloads and reduced fuel consumption are considerable: it is reported (3) that a weight saving of 100kg results in a cost saving of more than \$1000 in a normal truck lifetime. Rather less clear however, is the cost premium that the industry will bear for increased performance or weight saved on a particular component. In contrast, the benefits of reduced weight in aircraft are both more substantial and more easily defined, amounting to around £1500 and £1000 for every kg saved in military and civil craft respectively. Indeed, it was against this background, and prompted by a strong competitive threat from carbon-polymer composites, that Al-Li alloys were developed. Despite their higher cost, Boeing predict that up to 30% of aircraft weight may be composed of these alloys by 1990. Replacement of wrought alloys in the primary structure of a 747 would result in a weight saving of 10te, due to the higher specific stiffness properties.

This paper describes some new developments with short alumina fibres supplied by ICI PLC under the tradename 'Saffil'. It explores the potential for attaining higher performance levels by extrusion of powder-based composites and the opportunities for further weight reductions offered by a low density alumina fibre and magnesium matrix composites.

TABLE 1

Key material properties of engine components

Component	Operating Temp (°C)	σ_f	E_a	E_b	σ_t/σ_c	CTE	Wear Resistance	TC
Piston Crown Ring & Boss	250-500	•			•	•	•	•
Connecting Rod	130-180	•	•			•		
Piston Pin	180	•		•		•		
Cylinder Liner				•		•	•	•
Inlet Valve	600	•				•	•	
Valve Guide	200					•	•	•

E_a, b = Axial, Bending Stiffness TC = Thermal Conductivity
 σ_f, t, c = Fatigue/Tensile/Compressive Strength

FIBRE PRODUCTION AND PROPERTIES

The alumina fibres are produced as short staple by a solution spinning process which controls the fibre diameter within tight limits around a median value of 3 microns. The process is also quite unique in restricting the non-fibrous ("shot") content to very low levels, in sharp contrast to methods used to prepare whiskers and melt-spun ceramic fibres. The presence of "shot" is known to have an adverse effect on component surface finish and machine tool life. When present in composites these non-fibrous inclusions also act as crack initiation sites and thus have a profound effect on fatigue properties, particularly at room temperature. The reinforcement grades of fibre described in this paper contained less than 0.1% w/w and typically less than 0.05% w/w "shot". Failure to comply with the same high quality control standards will cause unacceptable scatter in test data and may lead to premature component failure.

During heat treatment of the as-spun fibres, after the removal of volatiles, crystallisation proceeds via the transition alumina group, with the time-temperature conditions controlling the rate of conversion from one form to another. The structural species present in the spinning solution and the nature of the atmosphere during decomposition are influential in determining the precise sequence of phases observed, but of major importance is the effect of a small amount of silica ($\sim 4\%$) in establishing the microstructure.

The presence of silica in the fibre enables a controlled progression through the transition alumina series with the gradual removal of porosity and increase in crystal size, crystallinity and density. The structural changes observed by X-ray diffraction methods are due to differences in the distribution of Al ions in the interstices of a cubic close-packed oxygen lattice.

The first crystalline phase observed is eta alumina. Fibre in this form has a crystal size of 50 - 60Å and an apparent density of 2.1 g/cm³. The low density can be accounted for by the presence of pores which are around 60Å size and uniformly distributed throughout the structure. Tensile strength and modulus values for this fibre typically fall within the ranges 1200 - 1500 MPa for strength and 150 - 200 GPa for modulus.

Further heating of the eta phase will result in progression through the gamma, delta and alpha alumina forms. Property changes associated with these transformations are summarised in table 2. It will be apparent from these data that by selecting a particular phase or combination of phases it is possible to vary key fibre properties such as strength, modulus, hardness and density. For example, fibre in the delta alumina form with a very low level of alpha alumina present has a tensile strength of 2000 MPa, a modulus of 300 GPa, a hardness on the Moh scale of 7 and a density of 3.3 g/cm³. With increasing concentration of the alpha alumina phase in the fibre the strength decreases and the modulus, hardness and density increase. The strength falls because there is a step increase in crystal size associated with the transformation from delta to alpha alumina from around 300Å to more than 2000Å, a change which is difficult to accommodate in a small diameter fibre.

Whereas fibre containing mainly delta alumina (RF) would be preferred for composite applications requiring high strength, fibre with a higher level of the harder alpha alumina phase (RG) might be preferred where the main requirement is improved wear resistance. Applications for the eta alumina (RD) fibre have not yet been identified, but the property package may provoke interest in the fibre as a reinforcement since composite density will continue to fall below that of aluminium with increasing volume fraction of fibre.

TABLE 2

Effect of alumina phase changes on fibre properties

Phase of Alumina (Eta)→(Gamma)→(Delta)→(Delta + Alpha)→(Alpha + Mullite)			
Fibre Grade:	RD	RF	RG
Mean Crystal Size (Å)	50-60	~300	2000+
Crystallinity (%)	50-55	~85	100
Pore Volume (mm ³ /g)	150-200	~50	0
Density (g/cm ³)	2.0-2.2	3.1-3.3	3.7
Tensile Strength (MPa)	1200-1500	1500-2000	~500
Modulus (GPa)	150-200	250-300	~360
Hardness (Moh Scale)	5	7	9

COMPOSITE FABRICATION

Most of the composites described in this paper were made by metal infiltration of bonded fibre preforms, using a small experimental rig at ICI. This technique for selectively reinforcing the most highly stressed region of a component, for example the crown of a piston, is currently the subject of world-wide investigation by the motor industry.

In the preparation of preforms a small amount of silica is used to bond the fibres, thus improving handling and machining properties. The binder is also effective in increasing the compressive strength of the preform in order to resist permanent deformation during high pressure casting. Careful control over casting conditions ensures that any deformation/densification of the preform during the course of melt infiltration is completely reversible. (4)

Good quality, pore-free billets were prepared using a melt superheat temperature of around 200°C and a pressure of 30 MPa. The die (300°C) and preform (750°C) were preheated to ensure complete metal infiltration. A particular feature of all of the composites made in this way is the high fibre-matrix bond strength achieved. The high pressure used in squeeze casting ensures a good mechanical bond, but this is enhanced by slight chemical interactions at the fibre surface. Magnesium present in aluminium alloys is known to be particularly effective in this respect.(5)

For the composites prepared using magnesium alloy, a protective cover gas of SF₆ in CO₂ was used over the crucible, launder and die throughout the melting and pouring operations. All other casting conditions in terms of melt superheat, die temperature and infiltration pressure were very similar to those employed for the preparation of aluminium matrix composites.

The composites made by powder metallurgy were prepared by DWA Specialty Composites, Chatsworth, California, using a proprietary process. They were supplied in the form of 160mm diameter billets and extruded bar of rectangular cross-section (77mm x 13mm). The extrudate had been processed through a sheer-face extrusion die.

POWDER METALLURGY

The measured properties of squeeze cast aluminium alloys reinforced with short staple alumina fibres are adequate to justify immediate material substitution in pistons and various other parts of the engine, however in components such as the connecting rod and piston pin further optimisation of properties will be required to replace steel without a significant increase in section thickness. In the piston pin, where the main aim is to avoid ovality of the cross-section in service, the key material properties are high bending stiffness, fatigue strength and wear resistance, and a low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). The target properties for this application have been attained by unidirectionally reinforced aluminium alloys, but the high cost of the fibres has prevented widespread usage. Similar financial constraints have limited the use of long, aligned fibres to prototype connecting rod parts. Whilst the use of hybrid systems of short and long fibres may have certain technical and cost benefits, there are obvious attractions in developing a low cost, short aligned fibre composite for these applications.

It is now widely appreciated that higher performance levels should be possible with short fibre MMCs through an improved understanding of the effects of strong fibre-matrix interactions on interfacial bonding and microstructure, however fibre alignment by extrusion processing provides a complimentary and perhaps shorter term solution. The powder metallurgy (PM) route offers a convenient means of producing billet feedstock for secondary processing operations such as extrusion, with the opportunity then for achieving controlled fibre orientation effects. Also, with improved powder production techniques leading to new alloying possibilities, there are potential property advantages over cast products due to the refined microstructures which result.

The tensile data presented in table 3 were recorded for Al6061 alloy reinforced with 20 and 30 v/o delta alumina fibre after T6 heat treatment. Some fracture toughness values ($K_{Q,BS 5447}$) obtained by RAE, Farnborough, are also given. The UTS of the compressed billets with a 2-D random distribution of fibres (figure 1) were below those recorded for equivalent squeeze cast billets, but the extruded material showed considerably better properties in the axial direction. The difference in axial and transverse properties of the extrudate however was not as great as might have been expected given the good alignment of fibres (Figure 2), probably due to the severe fibre breakdown which occurred on extrusion. The mean fibre length in the compressed billet was good at 90 microns, but this fell to around 10 microns in the extrudate, below the critical length for effective reinforcement of the alloy.

Clearly the technical target in future work is to increase fibre aspect ratio after extrusion; the full benefits of fibre alignment should then be reflected in more attractive axial strength, modulus, fatigue and expansion properties. However, the extent to which the material will penetrate automotive markets will depend on the bearable cost premium for a particular application. For applications outside of this sector, in for example aircraft parts, the financial constraints should not be as severe.

Figure 1. Showing the fibre orientations in a compressed PM billet

Figure 2. Showing the fibre orientation in an extruded PM section

TABLE 3

Properties of powder metallurgy (PM) and squeeze cast (SC) composites based on Al6061 (T6)

Fabrication Route	Fibre Orientation	V_f	E (GPa)	0.2% PS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Strain (%)	K_Q MPa \sqrt{m}
PM	2-D random	0.2	89.3	349	392	0.9	
PM	2-D random	0.3	97.1	380	417	0.8	
PM/Extruded	Axial	0.2	93.5	383	475	1.9	15.2, 13.4
PM/Extruded	Transverse	0.2	91.2	378	434	1.5	15.6, 14.8
SC	2-D random	0.2	90.2	321	425	1.2	

LOW DENSITY FIBRE COMPOSITES

The availability of high strength 7000 series alloys with good fatigue, corrosion and toughness properties resulted in greater emphasis being placed on the development of new materials such as Al-Li alloys with higher specific properties. Also significant was the fact that reducing material density has a far greater impact on structural weight savings than increasing strength, modulus or fracture toughness. (6)

With the current materials scene highly receptive to the opportunities presented by a low density reinforcing fibre, composites were prepared with matrices of LMO (commercial purity Al), LM10 (Al-10% Mg) and Al6061 (Al-1% Mg, 0.6% Si, 0.2% Cu, 0.25% Cr) and the RD alumina fibre described earlier. These alloys were selected because they had been the subject of earlier investigations with the delta alumina (RF) fibre and were reasonably well understood. The LMO and LM10 composites were examined in the as-cast condition but the Al6061 materials were subjected to various heat treatments as the programme progressed.

Density measurements on the LMO-20v/o fibre composites, using a mercury immersion technique after first coating in graphite to prevent reaction with the aluminium, were in line with theoretical predictions: 2.56g/cm³ for the eta alumina composite and 2.77g/cm³ for the delta alumina material. Since it is possible to incorporate 30-40v/o fibre in alumina by squeeze casting, the opportunity exists for achieving densities of 2.52-2.46 g/cm³, ie below those achieved by Al-Li alloys.

Room temperature tensile strength and modulus data on the LM10- and Al6061- based composites are summarized in table 4. The Al6061 materials were given a T6 heat treatment (530°C for 8 hours, water quench and then aged 160°C for 24 hours); the RF fibre composite was first homogenized at 495°C for 24 hours.

TABLE 4

Tensile data for 20 v/o RF and LD fibre composites

Alumina fibre	Matrix	Heat treatment	Modulus-E (GPa)	UTS σ (MPa)	Strain (%)
Delta (RF)	6061	-	92	283	1.7
Eta (RD)	6061	-	71	168	1.9
-	6061	T6	71	310	-
Delta (RF)	6061	T6	90	426	1.0
Eta (RD)	6061	T6	75	154	2.0
-	LM10	-	70	190	4.5
Delta (RF)	LM10	-	99	333	1.4
Eta (RD)	LM10	-	79	249	0.9

The results showed major differences in the response of the two Al6061 fibre systems to T6 heat treatment. Whereas the strength of the RF fibre composite was increased by about 50% to 426 MPa, approximately 37% higher than the unreinforced alloy, the strength of the RD fibre composite was relatively unaffected by the treatment. The properties of the low density system were much better in LM10 however, with the UTS increased by 30% over the unreinforced alloy and the modulus higher by 13%. Using these data the specific property terms shown in table 5 were calculated. Clearly the best properties belong to the RF fibre composites, but the specific stiffness terms for the RD fibre composites are significantly better than those of the unreinforced alloys.

TABLE 5

Specific stiffness and strength of composites containing 20v/o fibre.

Alumina fibre	Matrix	Composite density ρ (g/cm ³)	$\frac{E}{\rho}$	$\frac{E^{1/2}}{\rho}$	$\frac{\sigma^{1/2}}{\rho}$
-	6061 (T6)	2.68	26.5	1.55	6.57
Delta (RF)	6061 (T6)	2.80	32.1	1.60	7.37
Eta (RD)	6061 (T6)	2.57	29.2	1.64	4.83
-	LM10	2.63	26.6	1.57	5.24
Delta (RF)	LM10	2.72	36.4	1.70	6.71
Eta (RD)	LM10	2.53	31.2	1.70	6.24

SEM examination of the LM10 composites using a Link analyser with digimapping programme provided an explanation of the poor tensile strength data recorded for the RD fibre Al6061 composites. Concentration profiles were constructed for the main elements present in the matrix, interface and fibre regions. The most striking observation was that the magnesium

concentration increased sharply in the interfacial zone and to a depth of around 1 micron into the fibre (figure 3). There was no evidence of magnesium penetrating the delta alumina fibre, but regions close to the fibre boundaries and interdendritic precipitates were enriched with magnesium. Such segregation effects can be expected to have a significant influence on fibre - matrix bonding and fracture behaviour, but will have only a small effect on matrix properties in view of the high level of magnesium present in the alloy. In Al6061 however, in view of the low level of alloying additions, any redistribution of elements will have a critical effect on the strength of the matrix. Microhardness values (MHV) confirmed that this indeed was the situation. The data in table 6 show the effect of homogenisation treatment (495°C) and time of solution treatment (530°C) on the matrix microhardness in the RD fibre composites, prior to a precipitation treatment of 160° for 24 hours. Comparative data are given for the unreinforced alloy and for the RF fibre composite.

Figure 3. Showing penetration of magnesium into porous RD fibres

TABLE 6

Effect of heat treatment on the microhardness value of Al6061-20v/o fibre composites

Alumina fibre	Homogenisation time (hrs) at 495°C	MHV after (hr) solution time at 530°C and ageing 160°C 24 hours.				
		(1)	(2)	(4)	(8)	(16)
-	-	128	134	134	138	121
Delta (RF)	-					
Eta (RD)	-	134	106	120	87	60
-	24	137	131	138	136	-
Delta (RF)	24				143	
Eta (RD)	24				66	

Data for the RD fibre composite are in line with the microstructural observations made earlier and with the poor tensile data recorded. Homogenisation treatment served only to exacerbate the decline in matrix hardness with increasing solution treatment time, pushing values closer to that of the unalloyed aluminium (MHV about 30). In contrast, the hardness of the unreinforced alloy was relatively unaffected by homogenisation or time of solution treatment and there was no evidence of matrix weakening in the high density composite.

Analytical T.E.M examination of Al6061 composites showed the presence of a magnesium enriched layer at the fibre/matrix interface. For the RF fibre composite magnesium was observed at a concentration of 1-2% at the interface and penetrating the fibre to a depth of 250Å, equivalent to one crystallite thickness. In the RD fibre composite magnesium penetration was seen to extend to a much greater depth, up to 1 micron into the fibres. In both cases other alloying constituents such as iron, copper and chromium remained evenly distributed in the matrix. In the higher magnesium alloy LM10, a similar penetration of magnesium was seen but at a concentration in the RD fibre of around 50%. The magnesium did not appear to be present in metallic form and it may be that a reaction with silica has provided the driving force for its initial incorporation into the fibre.

The ability of the porous, low density fibres to extract selectively magnesium from aluminium alloys (there was no sign of aluminium metal within the pore structure) may lead to non-MMC applications. However, if the material is to find use as a reinforcement it will be necessary to restrict interactions with alloying additives to a very thin interfacial layer. Fibre coatings may prove useful, but careful selection of the alloy will be of paramount importance. The 2000 series alloys may provide a more suitable matrix in view of the uniform copper concentration profiles observed in work to date.

MAGNESIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

With current automotive design emphasis placed on the production of lighter weight vehicles the low density of magnesium offers obvious attractions, particularly when combined with the additional advantages over aluminium of faster casting production rates and longer machine tool life. The case for magnesium has been further strengthened by the introduction of new alloys with improved corrosion resistance and high temperature properties, and by a steady decline in recent years of the Mg:Al cost ratio making magnesium competitive on a unit volume basis. As an example of the weight saving opportunity presented by magnesium, in the Volvo LPC 2000 experimental car designed for maximum fuel economy, 50kg magnesium replaced 200kg steel in the transmission, clutch, steering rack housing, wheels, rear suspension, sub-frame etc. Reinforcement of magnesium with alumina fibres may extend its usefulness to the hotter parts of the engine where improved fatigue, stiffness, wear and expansion properties are required.

To investigate the potential of magnesium matrix composites, billets were prepared by metal infiltration of silica and alumina bonded alumina fibre preforms. For these first experiments the materials selected were commercial purity magnesium (99.9% pure) of density 1.73 g/cm^3 and delta alumina (RF) fibre of density 3.3 g/cm^3 . This combination, at a fibre volume fraction of 0.2, yielded a composite density of 2.08 g/cm^3 . Microscopic examination of the two billets showed that good infiltration had been achieved, with no evidence of preform deformation or residual porosity. Unfortunately, closer inspection revealed microstructural variations in both materials due to reaction between the matrix and the binders used (8).

In the silica bonded system, approximately 85% of the reinforced area from the top surface of the casting contained single phase matrix, with the rest composed of Mg and Mg_2Si eutectic. Also, in the bottom 1.5-2mm of the casting near the die base, high concentrations of primary Mg_2Si and eutectic Mg/ Mg_2Si were observed (Figure 4). A 10 sec. etching with Keller's solution was sufficient to highlight the angular blue plates of Mg_2Si . It is believed that the liquid metal infiltration front reacted with the silica binder and was swept through the preform in solution. The microstructural differences noted can then be explained in terms of the silica concentration profile throughout the thickness of the casting. Separation of Mg_2Si resulted in depletion of silica from the immediate vicinity of the precipitates causing a 'halo' effect of primary Mg. Beyond this region the silicon concentration in the matrix was sufficiently high to promote eutectic solidification.

Structural heterogeneity was also observed in the other billet due to reaction with the alumina binder used. A 20 sec exposure to a 10% solution of $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ was used to identify the $\text{Mg}_{12}\text{Al}_{17}$ reaction product (figure 5) which increased in concentration through the body of the casting. This concentration profile has been created in the same way as that of Mg_2Si in the billet using the silica bonded preform.

Figure 4. Showing large plates of Mg_2Si formed by reaction with the silica binder.

Figure 5. Showing grains of $\text{Mg}_{12}\text{Al}_{17}$ after reaction with the alumina binder.

CONCLUSIONS

- 1 Extrusion processing of short (RF) fibre composites provides a means of controlling fibre orientation and, by reducing fibre damage, an opportunity to narrow the performance gap with more expensive long fibre composites: replacement of steel in for example connecting rods and piston pins then becomes a realistic technical target.
- 2 The porous eta alumina (RD) fibres have been found to extract magnesium selectively from the matrix alloy. Such interactions need to be prevented or inhibited if the advantage of low fibre density is to be exploited in high strength, heat treatable alloys.
- 3 In order to realise the full potential of squeeze cast magnesium matrix composites it will be necessary to develop a stable binder system for the alumina fibre preforms.

REFERENCES

- 1 Dinwoodie, J., Moore, E. and Langman, C.A.J., The properties and applications of short staple alumina fibre reinforced aluminium alloys. Presented at ICCM-V, San Diego, California, July 30-August 1, 1985.
- 2 Dinwoodie, J., Automotive applications for MMCs based on short staple alumina fibres. Presented at SAE International Exposition, Detroit, Michigan, February 23-27, 1987.
- 3 Kittilsen, B., How to expand the market for magnesium wrought products. Proceedings IMA, New York, May 19-21, 1985.
- 4 Clyne, T.W. and Bader, M.G., Analysis of a squeeze infiltration process for fabrication of metal matrix composites. ICCM-V, San Diego, July 30-August 1, 1985.
- 5 Cappleman, G.R., Watts, J.F. and Clyne, T.W., The interface region in squeeze-infiltrated composites containing δ -alumina fibre in an aluminium matrix. J. Mater Sci., 1985, 20.
- 6 Ekvall, J.C. ASTM Spec. Technical Pub. No 761, 1982, p. 328.
- 7 Briscoe, N., TEM Study of 'Saffil' fibre reinforced aluminium composites. ICI Internal Report.
- 8 Martin, J., The effects of silica and alumina binders on 'Saffil' fibre reinforced magnesium. ICI Internal Report.